

Map of carbon storage capacity for European for marine habitats

Deliverable 4.5

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The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 4.5 overview

This report presents maps of the organic carbon (OC) storage capacity in European seas based on the OC content of upper sediment layers, environmental predictors and a scoring system translating OC content to a 5-level score as well as to a 3-level score better suited for visual presentation. The environmental predictors of OC content identified in **Deliverable 4.3** (Lønborg et al. 2024) as well as the Blue Carbon Index (BCI) scoring system developed in **Deliverable 4.4** (Graversen et al. 2024) have enabled mapping of the capacity to store OC in marine sediments.

The maps will then be used to optimise Marine spatial planning (MSP) for protecting marine carbon stores and to further understanding the relationships between biodiversity and carbon content of the seafloor (WP5). Finally, the approach can be also used to guide future predictions of OC storage capacity.

Introduction

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has defined Blue Carbon as “all biologically driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management”. So far, the Blue Carbon concept has mainly referred to marine sediment organic carbon (OC) that is captured and stored below seagrass meadows, tidal marshes, and mangrove forests, which have a high capacity for OC storage and can all be managed through protection and restoration of lost ecosystems. Protection of their OC stocks may help reduce the risk that the carbon is degraded and released as CO₂ while restoration of lost habitats may increase OC storage and, thereby, contribute to mitigation of climate change. Such management also supports biodiversity, coastal protection, nutrient retention, and other key ecological functions and services (Nellemann et al. 2009, Duarte et al. 2013; Howard et al. 2014; Hilmi et al, 2021).

Protecting the seafloor Blue Carbon from disturbances may help reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Howard et al. 2023, Epstein & Roberts 2022). Efficient protection requires knowledge on the variability in sediment OC levels, the factors controlling these, and a scoring system allowing a classification of sediment Blue Carbon levels across sea basins.

In this report we present maps of predicted OC levels (based on environmental predictors) in marine sediments (top 10 cm) and a proposed Blue Carbon Index (BCI) in European seas. This spatial information can be used to optimise Marine Spatial Planning, for example by indicating where marine protected areas (MPAs) would benefit OC storage in addition to biodiversity. The tools can also be further developed to guide future predictions of OC storage capacity. The report focuses on OC content (i.e. concentration in sediment samples, in percentage of the dry weight) rather than OC stocks (amount of OC stored per m² over a defined depth) or OC accumulation rate (amount of OC accumulated per m² per year) because the dataset on OC content is, by far, the most extensive.

Methods

Mapping predicted OC in European seas

The statistical analysis and sediment OC model presented in Deliverable 4.3 (Lønborg et al. 2024), identified some environmental factors that might drive the OC levels of marine sediments. The environmental data used in the model represented long-term (decadal) annual averages (Assis et al. 2024). It should thus be kept in mind that these are at a much coarser spatial resolution (never better than 1 km²) than the sediment samples in our database which would be georeferenced at least at ~ 100 m accuracy. However, environmental data associated with the samples is more limited and would represent the conditions at the time of sampling rather than the prevailing background conditions which are what is important for modelling. Here we have improved the model by adding drivers relating to seafloor features. This includes topographic variation or heterogeneity, also called rugosity, terrain ruggedness and geomorphic features, but all measured as the variation in slope around adjacent geographic cells (Bio-Oracle v3.0, Assis et al., 2024). We also included landscape features manually delimited from bathymetry which emphasised offshore features (Harris et al. (2014).

We have applied a new model to map predicted OC (top 10 cm) at the European sea basins scale using boosted regression trees (BRT). This was used because the previously used extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) as in Deliverable 4.3 (Lønborg et al. 2024), has limited ability to dealing with categorical data, that is the landscape features. Since EMODnet substrata data are not available for all the MPA Europe study area (Figure 1) they could not be incorporated in the model.

Mapping BCI score in European seas

The provisional BCI scoring system developed in Deliverable 4.4 (Graversen et al., 2024) was applied to the predicted OC map at European scale, using a five-level index:

- 1 (very low): 0-0.4 %OC
- 2 (low): 0.4-0.8 %OC
- 3 (moderate): 0.8-1.5 %OC
- 4 (high): 1.5-2.5 %OC
- 5 (very high): >2.5 %OC

For the rationale behind the BCI see Deliverable 4.4 (Graversen et al., 2024). QGIS v3.28.3 (2022) software was used to convert the predicted OC to BCI scores. The suitability of this scoring system for communicating information on OC will be examined in this Deliverable.

For visualization on European-scale Blue Carbon maps, we also applied a simpler 3-level score (Score 1 (low): 0-0.5 %OC; Score 2 (intermediate): 0.5-2 %OC; Score 3 (high): >0.5 % OC). The 3-level scores were adapted from the 5-level scores and supported by further examples of low-high OC levels reported in the literature (Premuzic et al., 1982; Hedges & Keil, 1995; Zimmerman & Canuel, 2000; Hyland et al., 2005; Kennedy & Björk, 2009; Dahl et al, 2016; Kindeberg et al., 2018, 2019; Middelburg et al, 2009).

Spatial analyses

Statistics on geographic cells were applied at European marine regional scale within the boundaries of the exclusive economic zones (EEZs) using QGIS v3.28.3 (2022).

Results and Discussion

The model results

With the additional data on wave fetch, geomorphic features, and terrain ruggedness, the BRT model had a better predictive value than the model XGBoost in Deliverable 4.3 (Lønborg et al. 2024) (Figure 2). The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF, i.e. measure of multicollinearity, Table 1) and the pairs plot (Figure 3) showed that the slope (expressing depth changes over distance) was highly correlated with terrain ruggedness (expressing depth changes between adjacent focal cells). Given the high correlation between slope and terrain ruggedness, only slope was considered in the model.

Of the thirteen predictor variables of sediment OC levels, wave fetch (21%), distance from coast (12%), and max temperature (11%), were key explanatory factors (Figure 2, Appendix 1, Figure A3). These were followed by geomorphic features (8%), solar radiation and slope (7%), salinity, bathymetry and seawater speed (6%). The remaining environmental predictors described less than 5% of the variation of predicted OC levels within European seas.

OC levels increased with lower wave fetch, lower maximum temperature, and gentler slope, as well as with closer proximity to the shore, higher available radiation, higher nitrate levels and higher salinity (Figures 4, 5). We interpret this to be because organic matter (a) arises from land based and marine sources, e.g., seagrass and alga production in well-lit conditions, (b) is concentrated in fine particles which settle in wave-sheltered conditions, and (c) decomposes less in colder conditions. This outcome makes sense as both sheltered cold near shore sites with high productivity and deep sedimentation basins support high OC levels while.

The model-predicted OC at a 1 km resolution was difficult to visualize in a European-scale figure. Therefore, the predicted OC map is shown with equal area hexagon maps at 25 km and 50 km resolution, at linear and log scales (Figures 6, 7, 8, 9).

The model predicted that the Black Sea had the highest mean OC (mean = 0.55) (Table 3), while the other marine regions had lower and relatively similar mean OC (0.25-0.38). However, all regions showed high variability and a similar range of OC levels (Table 3). At the national level, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Netherlands had the highest and lowest values of predicted OC (mean = 2.92 and 0.05), respectively (Table 4).

The Blue Carbon Index

The predicted OC map with a spatial resolution of 1 km was converted to a BCI score map, using the 5-point and 3-point scales (Figures 10, 11). We propose the 3-point scale as superior for visualisation of the patterns.

As expected, the model predicted that the majority of the offshore European seabed contained very low or low OC values, while coastal areas varied between low and moderate OC content respectively (Figures 10, 11). Off-shore areas with high OC content were predicted in the Baltic, Black and White Seas. A close up analysis of the predicted OC map and sampled data, showed they were closely correlated, with most high OC in coastal waters, especially in wave sheltered lochs, fjords, and bays (where often trawling and dredging is prohibited but not always) (Figures 13, 14).

Considering the overlap between the above mentioned areas with high and very high OC values with available data on EMODnet Geology seabed substrata and EUSeaMap broadscale seabed habitats (Figure 1), it is possible to see the correspondence between high OC and the presence of fine mud to muddy sand sediments (data not shown).

Of the environmental variables explaining the variation in OC in the model (Table 2), only wave fetch showed a trend in relation to the BCI scores, i.e., a (relatively) clear negative relationship with exposure (Figures 15, 16). However, within each variable there is a high variability in the range of drivers associated with each of the scores.

Next steps:

- Reduce the number of environmental variables to avoid an overparameterized model, removing those variables that have less than 5% of contribution and/or select only one of those that are high correlated.
- Replace Harris geomorphic data in the model with geomorphic data in EMODnet.
- Consider whether and how to improve the use of categorical data (e.g. landscape geomorphic features), and the riverine run-off data if available at European scale.
- Run both BRT and XGBoost models with complete and final blue carbon dataset to provide an assessment of their advantages and limitations in the OC prediction, and a more accurate European map of OC.

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Table 1. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of environmental predictors. VIF is a measure of the amount of multicollinearity in a set of multiple regression variables.

Variables	VIF
Seawater Speed	1.26
Diffuse Attenuation	1.99
Phosphate	2.20
Salinity	2.61
Distance Shore	2.94
Bathymetry	3.21
Available Radiation	4.01
Wave Fetch	4.71
Temperature Max	5.01
Temperature Min	5.57
Nitrate	6.47
Slope	9.27
Terrain Ruggedness	9.43

Table 2a. Descriptive statistics for the environmental predictors. The minimum, 1st (25 percentage) quartile, average values, median, 3rd (75 percentage) quartile and maximum are shown for each blue carbon index (BCI) 5-level scale.

BCI Score	Environmental variable (Units)	Minimum	1 st quartile	Median	Mean	3 rd quartile	Maximum
1	Wave Fetch (km)	181	16246	34128	34285	52179	64000
2		735	12232	34560	32570	52780	64000
3		501	4524	18342	24097	43727	64000
4		220	1885	10181	21364	44692	64000
5		175	799	3986	15564	30251	64000
1	Distance from shore (km)	0.00	0.03	0.17	0.77	0.86	12.07
2		0.00	0.02	0.16	0.64	0.77	8.37
3		0.00	0.01	0.05	0.44	0.33	8.27
4		0.00	0.01	0.03	0.31	0.30	7.45
5		0.00	0.00	0.01	0.22	0.14	5.74
1	Temperature Maximum(°C)	-0.96	11.40	13.76	13.70	16.33	27.99
2		-0.95	7.71	12.84	11.40	14.92	26.61
3		-0.81	9.68	13.16	12.11	14.95	26.69
4		-0.72	7.92	13.24	12.10	15.19	26.31
5		0.87	7.74	13.75	12.85	16.80	25.99
1	Available Radiation	19.60	26.27	28.39	29.79	34.23	44.60
2		10.13	24.86	27.44	29.55	34.87	45.54
3		10.41	23.71	26.01	28.18	31.62	45.39
4		10.13	23.31	26.04	27.39	30.29	44.84
5		11.28	23.39	27.31	27.21	29.38	40.02
1	Slope	0.01	0.15	0.51	1.12	1.40	15.29
2		0.00	0.28	0.79	1.71	1.95	36.25
3		0.03	0.36	0.96	1.97	2.44	31.99
4		0.01	0.28	1.17	2.69	3.60	26.52
5		0.00	0.32	0.93	2.13	2.41	37.78

Table 2b. Descriptive statistics for the environmental predictors. The minimum, 1st (25 percentage) quartile, average values, median, 3rd (75 percentage) quartile and maximum are shown for each blue carbon index (BCI) 3-level scale.

BCI Score	Environmental variable (Units)	Minimum	1st quartile	Median	Mean	3rd quartile	Maximum
1	Wave Fetch (km)	181	15511	34085	34095	52176	64000
2		244	4955	22340	24627	48644	64000
3		176	877	4737	16103	30407	64000
1	Distance Shore (km)	0.00	0.03	0.16	0.77	0.88	12.07
2		0.00	0.01	0.07	0.46	0.47	8.38
3		0.00	0.00	0.01	0.22	0.14	6.86
1	Temperature Maximum (°C)	-0.96	11.32	13.70	13.47	16.14	26.69
2		-0.85	8.14	13.03	11.71	14.95	26.70
3		0.87	7.78	13.71	12.83	16.69	25.99
1	Available Radiation	19.60	25.96	28.18	29.66	34.31	44.60
2		10.13	23.80	26.51	28.58	32.99	45.54
3		10.89	23.35	27.23	27.21	29.37	44.72
1	Slope	0.00	0.15	0.52	1.19	1.44	15.30
2		0.00	0.34	0.95	2.09	2.67	36.25
3		0.00	0.31	0.93	2.18	2.46	37.78

Table 3. Statistics for predicted sediment organic carbon (OC %, top 10 cm) at marine region level.

European Marine region	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Baltic Sea	0.38	0.50	0.00	21.05
Black Sea	0.55	0.39	0.01	13.92
North-East Atlantic Ocean	0.25	0.18	0.00	21.05
Mediterranean Sea	0.25	0.21	0.00	21.05

Table 4. Statistics for predicted sediment OC (% , top 10 cm) at the national level (within exclusive economic zone (EEZ)).

Country	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Albania	0.62	0.39	0.13	7.60
Algeria	0.32	0.13	0.02	3.32
Belgium	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.97
Bosnia and Herzegovina	2.92	1.42	0.27	4.89
Bulgaria	0.52	0.52	0.01	3.63
Croatia	0.47	0.45	0.01	21.05
Cyprus	0.27	0.15	0.05	11.41
Denmark	0.22	0.19	0.02	4.71
Denmark (Faeroe Islands)	0.15	0.07	0.02	3.80
Egypt	0.17	0.08	0.00	1.01
Estonia	0.37	0.28	0.02	7.98
Finland	0.34	0.42	0.01	12.34
France	0.24	0.14	0.06	6.18
Georgia	0.46	0.39	0.06	13.92
Germany	0.18	0.19	0.02	5.31
Greece	0.28	0.23	0.02	11.70
Iceland	0.20	0.10	0.02	4.33
Ireland	0.18	0.19	0.02	14.86
Israel	0.24	0.09	0.01	1.22
Italy	0.24	0.15	0.01	7.86
Latvia	0.38	0.30	0.02	1.93
Lebanon	0.27	0.10	0.01	2.12
Libya	0.20	0.09	0.01	2.92
Lithuania	0.27	0.18	0.02	3.25
Malta	0.19	0.12	0.06	3.76
Monaco	0.27	0.07	0.15	0.66
Montenegro	0.30	0.23	0.07	7.83
Morocco	0.30	0.16	0.02	2.75
Netherlands	0.05	0.08	0.00	5.06
Norway	0.30	0.24	0.02	13.91
Norway (Jan Mayen)	0.19	0.06	0.09	1.77
Poland	0.33	0.28	0.01	9.85
Portugal	0.30	0.14	0.02	10.14
Portugal (Azores)	0.28	0.08	0.01	2.59
Portugal (Madeira)	0.41	0.19	0.01	4.63
Romania	0.90	0.56	0.01	2.61
Russia	0.41	0.31	0.03	10.09
Slovenia	0.46	0.35	0.18	3.01
Spain	0.31	0.21	0.03	8.31
Spain (Canary Islands)	0.60	0.27	0.01	3.99
Sweden	0.43	0.68	0.03	20.29
Syria	0.27	0.26	0.01	14.56
Tunisia	0.16	0.09	0.00	1.96
Turkey	0.40	0.36	0.01	14.51
Ukraine	0.58	0.42	0.02	10.32
United Kingdom	0.22	0.19	0.02	12.33
United Kingdom (Gibraltar)	0.79	1.68	0.11	11.44
United Kingdom (Guernsey)	0.22	0.11	0.06	2.62
United Kingdom (Jersey)	0.32	0.16	0.08	1.98

Figure 1. EMODnet Geology seabed substrata map (version 2019, Multiscale -Folk 5 classification (left) and EMODnet broad-scale seabed habitat map for Europe (EUSeaMap) (version 2023) habitat (EUNIS 2019) (right). Source EMODnet Geology (left) and Seabed Habitats (right) (last access: May 2024).

Figure 2. Relationship between the logarithm of observed organic carbon and model-predicted organic carbon (as OC in percentage; deviance explained: 0.625) (top). Frequency and data distribution of the logarithm of observed organic carbon (bottom).

Figure 3. Matrix of the Pearson's correlation (r) between all pairs of predictor variables, 0 (indicates no linear relationship) to 1 (indicates a perfect positive linear relationship) and direction (+/-) of the relationship between the two variables.

Figure 4a. Partial plots depicting the individual effect of each environmental variable on the response variable in the model (i.e. logarithm of percent organic carbon). The relative contribution of the variables are in parentheses.

Figure 4b. Partial plots depicting the individual effect of landscape geomorphic features on the response variable in the model (i.e. logarithm of percent organic carbon). The relative contribution of the variables are in parentheses.

Figure 5. The contribution of the environmental model variables to predicting the concentration of organic carbon (OC) in sediments in European seas.

Figure 6. Map of predicted organic carbon (OC in percentage) stored in marine sediments of European seas. Resolution of predictions is 25 km.

Figure 7. Map of log-transformed predicted organic carbon (OC in percentage) stored in marine sediments of European seas. Resolution of predictions is 25 km.

Figure 8. Map of predicted organic carbon (OC in percentage) stored in marine sediments of European seas. Resolution of predictions is 50 km.

Figure 9. Map of log-transformed predicted organic carbon (OC in percentage) stored in marine sediments of European seas. Resolution of predictions is 50 km.

Figure 10. Map of 5-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon (OC in percentage) of marine sediments in European seas and beyond the study area of MPA Europe. Resolution of predictions is 1 km. For the rationale behind the BCI see Deliverable 4.4 (Graversen et al., 2024).

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Figure 11. Map of 3-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon (OC in percentage) of marine sediments in European seas and beyond the study area of MPA Europe. Resolution of predictions is 1 km.

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Figure 12. Map of 3-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon with BC datapoints (OC in percentage) overlaid by the OC data from the field samples in the MPA Europe database. The resolution of predictions is 1 km. Black line boxes indicate break-up maps in Figures 13 and 14.

Figure 13. Sub-regional maps of 3-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon overlaid by the sample data (OC in percentage) of marine sediments in (A) northwest water of Scotland, and (B) southwest Swedish waters, Baltic Sea. Resolution of predictions is 1 km.

Figure 14. Sub-regional maps of 3-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon overlaid by sample data (OC in percentage) in (A) Romanian and Bulgarian of the Black Sea, and (B) Greek waters. Resolution of predictions is 1 km.

Figure 15. Boxplots showing the distribution of each of the 4 key environmental variables identified as potential drivers for organic carbon (OC) scores against the 5-level BCI scale: (A) wave fetch (or wave exposure); (B) distance to coast; (C) temperature maximum; and (D) available radiation. The horizontal bars represent the median, the boxes 25% and 75% percentiles, the whiskers the range but no further than 1.5 times the inter quartile range, and dots outliers.

Figure 16. Boxplots showing the distribution of each of the 4 key environmental variables identified as potential drivers for organic carbon (OC) scores against the 3-level BCI scale: (A) wave fetch (or wave exposure); (B) distance to coast; (C) temperature maximum; and (D) available radiation. The horizontal bars represent the median, the boxes 25% and 75% percentiles, the whiskers the range but no further than 1.5 times the inter quartile range, and dots outliers.

Figure 17. Plot of the environmental predictors added since the previous Deliverable report. (A) Boxplot (as in previous figures) showing the distribution of slope across the 5-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon (OC). (B) Stacked bar plot of geomorphic features illustrating the scoring distribution for predicted OC associated with geomorphic features. Each bar represents a blue carbon index (BCI) score and within each bar the stacks are divided and coloured by geomorphic features.

Figure 18. Plot of the new environmental predictors. (A) Boxplot showing the distribution of slope across the 3-level scale blue carbon index (BCI) for the predicted organic carbon (OC). (B) Stacked barplot of geomorphic features illustrating the scoring distribution for predicted OC associated with geomorphic features. Each bar represents a blue carbon index (BCI) score and within each bar the stacks are divided and coloured by geomorphic features.

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